

Atomic resolution analysis of Ag ion-exchanged zeolite A**

Alvaro Mayoral*, Thomas Carey, Paul A. Anderson, Axel Lubk, and Isabel Diaz

Zeolites can be defined as crystalline microporous aluminosilicates based on a framework of AlO_4 and SiO_4 tetrahedra connected by shared oxygen atom bridges, which can be combined leading to at least 176 unique zeolite framework types^[1], making zeolites among the most important and versatile heterogeneous catalysts^[2]. The properties of zeolites strongly depend on the pore shape, size and distribution making it possible in a reaction to select between reactants or products^[3]. As a result zeolites are widely employed in the fields of petroleum refining and petrochemistry, and also as desiccants, ion exchangers or molecular sieves, for example in water/air treatments^[4]. In addition to their structure-related properties, they can be also employed as bifunctional catalysts incorporating metals such as Ag, Pd, Pt or Cu within the framework. In order to characterize these guest elements incorporated within the zeolitic framework, conventional high-resolution transmission electron microscopy has been applied^[5]. Taking into account the good crystallinity and the large lattice parameters of the zeolites, it would be expected that they would provide excellent materials for transmission electron microscopy (TEM) analysis. However, this is far from the case and recording several micrographs from the same crystal has resulted in an almost impossible task, as most zeolites are tremendously sensitive to the electron beam. This sensitivity has

been related to radiolytic damage^[5a, 6], which decreases with increasing the acceleration voltage^[5b]. The most important factor in limiting the lifetime of zeolites under the electron beam is the Si/Al ratio. A Si-rich zeolite is more stable than one with a low Si/Al ratio. Furthermore, the type of cation incorporated into the framework has been found to have an influence on the zeolite beam sensitivity^[7].

For the case of scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) imaging, the scenario may be worse as the beam is concentrated into a very fine spot which can cause hole drilling above some threshold current density^[8]. However, if a slightly different approach is taken by using low-dose conditions, novel and excellent information may be achieved especially in combination with aberration corrected electron microscopes^[9]. With the implementation of aberration correctors^[10] in STEM microscopes, electron probes smaller than 1 Å have been achieved, allowing dynamic imaging of single atoms and clusters composed of a few atoms^[11].

The motivation for the present work rests on the application of C_s -corrected STEM-HAADF (where the contrast is related to Z^2) to study zeolite A (LTA structure type) which has a Si/Al ratio of 1 (the highest aluminum content possible and therefore the least stable zeolite under the electron beam). The incorporation of silver into this structure results in the formation of a material with antibacterial activity^[12] and with particular applications for the recovery of radioactive materials^[13].

In the present work the initial Na^+ cations present from the synthesis were replaced by Ag^+ ^[14], followed by a complete dehydration resulting in a spectacular sequence of color changes from white, in its hydrated form to orange when fully dehydrated^[15]. Kim and Seff attributed that color change to the presence of partially reduced Ag_6 octahedra in the sodalite cages (figure 1). In contrast, Jacobs *et al.*^[16] proposed that coloration was due to the presence of linear clusters Ag_3 (see top right cage in figure 1). Figure 1 shows the proposed model for the dehydrated AgA (silver zeolite A) where the red atoms correspond to oxygen and the Ag (grey) forms an octahedron inside the sodalite cage with 6–8 surrounding Ag atoms placed in the 6-rings (figure 1b).

In the present manuscript the crystallographic positions of zeolite and silver atoms were determined by Rietveld refinement against high resolution PXRD data (see supporting information S1). In preparation for electron microscopy, the material, initially preserved under inert atmosphere, was in contact with air for a few minutes (during crushing and microgrid deposition).

For the purposes of comparison both NaA (sodium zeolite A) and AgA (silver zeolite A) were imaged. Figure 2a shows the model for as-synthesized zeolite A^[1] $[\text{Na}^+_{12}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{27}]_8[\text{Al}_{12}\text{Si}_{12}\text{O}_{48}]_8$ (for clarity only Si, Al and O are shown). In this model, viewed along the [001] orientation, the red atoms, zeolite bridges, correspond to oxygen. Due to the low stability of the zeolites under the electron beam, minimum exposure time was used for the images (8 seconds per image), using a beam current of 1.65×10^{-10} A. The larger alpha cages together with the smaller sodalite ones (center) can be directly observed and corroborated by comparison with the model presented,

[*] Dr. A. Mayoral
Laboratorio de Microscopías Avanzadas (LMA), Instituto de Nanociencia de Aragón (INA), Universidad de Zaragoza, Mariano Esquillor, 50018, Zaragoza, Spain
Fax: +34 976 762776
E-mail: amayoral@unizar.es

T. Carey and Dr. P. A. Anderson
School of Chemistry
University of Birmingham((Institution))
Edgbaston, Birmingham, UK

Dr. A. Mayoral and Dr. A. Lubk
Transpyrenean Associated Laboratory for Electron Microscopy (TALEM)

Dr. A. Lubk
CEMES-CNRS, Groupe NanoMatériaux, Toulouse, France

Dr. I. Diaz
Instituto de Catálisis y Petroleoquímica, CSIC, Madrid, Spain

[**] TC acknowledges University of Birmingham, EPSRC and Diamond Light Source for funding and the AWM/EDRF-funded Birmingham Science City Advanced Materials 1 project for providing facilities and equipment. Many thanks to the Diamond Light Source for the provision of powder synchrotron X-ray diffraction facilities and to Chiu Tang, Julia Parker and Stephen Thompson for assistance in using beamline I11.

Supporting information for this article is available on the WWW under <http://www.angewandte.org> or from the author.

superimposed on the image (figure 2b), and on the simulation (figure 2c).

Figure 3 shows the C_s corrected STEM–HAADF images of dehydrated AgA along its main crystallographic orientations, [001], [011] and [111]. Due to the low stability of the zeolites under the electron beam each orientation was recorded on different crystallites as severe beam damage occurred. During a common scanning, the zeolite damage always started on the edge of particle, the thinnest area, producing a loss of crystallinity (see supporting information S2). Large differences were observed between this sample and the as-synthesized material. In the dehydrated AgA a perfect distribution of white spots coupled with the zeolite structure was observed. This extraordinary distribution was observed in all the crystallographic orientations (see figure 3 and supporting information S3) but no extra spots appeared in the FFT diffractogram. In addition, spheres with higher contrast, marked by white arrows in figure 3b, were also observed in coincidence with the zeolite cages.

If we analyze further the NaA images in figure 2, the black parts correspond to the parts with no mass, *i.e.* zeolite alpha cages, linked to each other by the sodalite cages, in which the 4 member rings can be clearly observed. In order to interpret the raw data obtained in the microscope, we must assume that at this level, we cannot distinguish between the framework atoms as they are very similar in terms of atomic number. By superimposing the zeolite model it is easy to understand the electron micrographs. The fact that the atoms forming the sodalite cage are faint and not completely resolved can be explained as a consequence, first of quick beam damage to the zeolite, which did not allow us to go to higher resolution, and secondly of the beam spread that the probe suffered when it passed through the crystal. In order to get a good fit between simulation and experiment the simulated HAADF image was convoluted with a Gaussian filter of 1.7 Å fwhm in a last step, effectively reducing the spatial (see supporting information S4).

For the ion-exchanged material (figure 4), owing to the great difference in atomic number between silver and the zeolitic framework the latter is virtually invisible and only 4 atomic columns forming squares or 9 columns^[15a] were identified (figure 4b). Figure 4b shows the atomic distribution where each unit contains 9 Ag atomic columns. By measuring the distances between the atoms placed in the corners we obtained a value of ~ 4.72 Å which can be attributed to Ag located at the 6-rings forming the sodalite cage. In the model obtained from Rietveld refinement, that distance was determined to be 4.76 Å, figure 4c. Meanwhile, the distance between Ag columns in the adjacent sodalite cages was found to be approximately 7.41 Å, cf. 7.57 Å in the model. In addition, to those four columns of atoms another, less bright, five can be observed. These atoms which are situated one in the center of the square and the other four on the sides of the square perfectly match with positions of the Ag octahedron Ag_6 presented in figure 1 (left upper corner). The intensity profiles plotted over 3 atomic columns in the sodalite cages, figure 4e, show a higher intensity on the corners due to the higher number of atoms in those positions. For the second line intensity profile (points 4, 5 and 6), atoms forming the Ag_6 cluster the highest value was obtained in the center of the octahedron, again attributed to the greater number of atoms in that column. For those atoms the interatomic distance was found to be 2.70 Å. To confirm all these assignments simulated STEM–HAADF was performed using the model proposed in figure 4d. The same contrast was obtained in the simulated data, unambiguously determining the silver atomic positions. In addition, a faint signal emanating from the Al, Si, O framework can be appreciated, figure 4f.

It can be seen from figure 4a that the Ag_6 octahedron did not appear in certain regions of the crystals, which instead contained clusters in the alpha cages that were absent from the Rietveld refinement (see supporting information S1). This suggests that these regions result from the short exposure to the atmosphere during manipulation of the material in preparing the microgrid. It is likely that water coordinates to the Ag^+ ions in the 6-rings that anchor the neutral Ag_6 clusters in the sodalite cages, drawing them into the alpha cages and releasing the Ag atoms to diffuse through the zeolitic structure, and end up forming larger nanoparticles in the alpha cages or on the surface of the crystals.

In summary, the present results demonstrate the ability of aberration-corrected STEM–HAADF to characterize at atomic resolution zeolite frameworks with different metal cations incorporated in the structure. The fact that the Si/Al ratio was 1 represents a huge step forward in the application of this technique, as it proves its genuine applicability to any of the 176 zeolitic framework types. With these results we have been able to image for the first time the silver arrangement in dehydrated silver-exchanged zeolite A first described by Kim and Seff^[15a] in 1977. We have been able to evidence the formation of a silver octahedron inside the sodalite cages surrounded by 8 cations each located in the center of a 6-ring. This method offers a real solution for in-depth characterization at the atomic level, including pore contents, of three dimensional porous solids widely employed in the petrochemicals industry, which is essential for a full understanding and better design of new catalysts.

Experimental Section

Synthesis: Na-A was synthesized using a standard verified zeolite A preparation^[17]. 8 g of the zeolite was then stirred in a 0.1 M solution of $AgNO_3$ (Sigma Aldrich, 99%), for 16 h at room temperature. The milky solution obtained was filtered and washed with 1 l of deionized water, in order to remove any salt remaining on the surface. Once the silver ion exchange was completed, the silver zeolite A was dehydrated at 425 °C for 12 h under 1×10^{-6} mbar. The material was then kept under argon gas in an argon glovebox before electron microscopic examination. For these measurements the vial was opened to air and deeply crushed using a mortar and pestle in order to obtain the thinnest crystals possible. Afterwards, the zeolite was dispersed in ethanol and a few drops of the suspension were deposited onto the lacey carbon copper microgrids (the total time of the procedure did not exceed 5 minutes).

Characterization: Powder synchrotron X-ray diffraction profiles were collected on beamline I11 ($\lambda = 0.825035$ Å) at the Diamond Light Source, UK. All samples were loaded into 0.5 mm diameter borosilicate glass capillaries and sealed using a small blowtorch flame. The scattered radiation was detected as a function of 2θ by the multi-analyzing crystals (MAC) detector with a step size of 0.005°.

Aberration-corrected STEM–HAADF data was acquired using a XFEG FEI TITAN 60–300 kV located at the Laboratorio de Microscopias Avanzadas LMA in the Institute of Nanoscience of Aragon (INA). This microscope was equipped with a high brightness field emission gun (XFEG), a monochromator and with a CEOS dodecapole aberration corrector for the electron probe. A beam convergence of 24.8 mrad half-angle has been used, yielding a calculated probe size of (0.7 Å). Figures 4b and 4c were Fourier filtered with the purpose of improving the signal to noise ratio (raw data is presented in supporting information S5).

Multisllice STEM simulations: To simulate the STEM–HAADF data of the NaA and AgA along the [001] orientation we used the QSTEM program^[18]. The dynamic scattering simulation is based on the multislice method. The crystal supercell dimensions used were $98.64 \times 98.64 \times 981.7$ Å³, where a maximum thickness of 981.7 Å³ has been found to be the limit which best fit to the experimental results. The

parameters used were: $C_s = 0$ mm, $U_{acc} = 300$ kV, HAADF collection angle = 70 to 200 mrad and convergence semiangle 24 mrad. For NaA the beam diameter was set to 1.7 Å; for AgA it was set to 0.7 Å.

Received: ((will be filled in by the editorial staff))

Published online on ((will be filled in by the editorial staff))

Keywords: Electronmicroscopy · Zeolites · Catalysts · Nanomaterials

- [1] C. Baerlocher, L. B. McCusker, http://www.iza-structure.org/databases/books/Atlas_6ed.pdf, **2011**.
- [2] A. Corma, *Chem. Rev.* **2007**, *97*, 2373-2419.
- [3] A. Philippou, M. W. Anderson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1994**, *116*, 5774-5783.
- [4] T. Masuda, T. Asanuma, M. Shouji, S. R. Mukai, M. Kawase, K. Hashimoto, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* **2003**, *58*, 649.
- [5] a) L. A. Bursill, E. A. Lodge, J. M. Thomas, *Nature* **1980**, 111-113; b) O. Terasaki, T. Ohsuna, V. Alfredson, J.-O. Bovin, D. Watanabe, K. Tsuno, *Ultramicroscopy* **1991**, *39*, 238-246; c) O. Terasaki, T. Ohsuna, *Topics in Catal.* **2003**, *24*, 13-18; d) J. M. Thomas, P. A. Midgley, *Chem. Comm.* **2004**, 1253-1267, 1253-1267; e) I. Díaz, E. Kokkoli, O. Terasaki, M. Tsapatsis, *Chem. Mater.* **2004**, *16*, 5226-5232; f) M. Choi, K. Na, J. Kim, Y. Sakamoto, O. Terasaki, R. Ryoo, *Nature* **2009**, *461*, 246-250; g) I. Díaz, A. Mayoral, *Micron* **2011**, *42*, 512-527; h) J. E. Readman, P. D. Barker, I. Gameson, J. A. Hriljac, W. Zhou, P. P. Edwards, P. A. Anderson, *Chem. Commun.* **2004**, 736.
- [6] a) M. M. J. Treacey, J. M. Newsam, *Ultramicroscopy* **1987**, *23*, 411-420; b) R. Csencsits, R. Gronsky, *Ultramicroscopy* **1987**, 421.
- [7] L. A. Bursill, J. M. Thomas, K. J. Rao, *Nature* **1981**, 157-158.
- [8] R. F. Egerton, P. Li, M. Malac, *Micron* **2004**, *35*, 399-409.
- [9] V. Ortolan, A. Uzun, B. C. Gates, N. D. Browning, *Nature Nanotechnology* **2010**, *5*, 506-510.
- [10] a) O. L. Krivanek, N. Delby, A. R. Lupini, *Ultramicroscopy* **1999**, *78*, 1; b) P. E. Baston, N. Dellby, O. L. Krivanek, *Nature* **2002**, *418*, 617.
- [11] A. Mayoral, D. A. Blom, M. M. Mariscal, C. Guiterrez-Wing, J. Aspiazu, M. Jose-Yacaman, *Chem. Commun.* **2010**, 46, 8758-8760.
- [12] a) Y. Inouea, M. Hoshino, H. Takahashi, T. Noguchi, T. Murata, Y. Kanzaki, H. Hamashima, M. Sasatsu, *Journal of Inorganic Biochemistry* **92** (2002) 37-42 **2002**, *92* 37-42; b) Y. Matsumura, K. Yoshikata, S. Kunisaki, T. Tsuchido, *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* **2003**, *69*, 4278-4281.
- [13] a) T. R. Thomas, B. A. Staples, L. P. Murphy, *Vol. 4088737*, United States, **1978**; b) O. B. Yang, Y. J. Kim, J. C. Kim, J. S. Lee., H. J. Yang, *Vol. 5457230* United States, **1995**.
- [14] P. A. Anderson, in *Molecular Sieves, Vol. 3*, Springer, Berlin, **2002**.
- [15] a) Y. Kim, K. Seff, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1977**, *99*, 7055-7057; b) A. Mayoral, P. A. Anderson, *Nanotechnology* **2007**, *18*, 165708.
- [16] P. A. Jacobs, J. B. Uytterhoeven, H. K. Beyer, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.* **1979**, *75*, 56.
- [17] H. Robson, K. P. Lillerud., *Syntheses of Zeolitic Materials. 2nd Edition*, **2001**.
- [18] C. T. Koch, Arizona State University **2002**.
-

Zeolites & electron microscopy

Alvaro Mayoral*, Thomas Carey, Paul A. Anderson, Axel Lubk, and Isabel Diaz

Page – Page

Atomic resolution analysis of Ag ion-exchanged zeolite A

Zeolites are porous solids which in all cases present a well-defined three dimensional structure formed of SiO_4 and AlO_4 tetrahedra extended over space. The large regular intracrystalline pore space, in combination with the ability of zeolites to incorporate metals within their structure, has led to these materials being among the most used petrochemical catalysts. Although electron microscopy has been successfully applied for the structure determination of certain zeolite types, the low stability under the electron beam has been a major drawback preventing more widespread and detailed characterization through this method. In the present work zeolite A (LTA type) has been synthesized by a conventional hydrothermal method followed by a silver ion exchange and finally dehydrated under high vacuum. Here, we prove that by controlling the beam current in an aberration-corrected microscope in STEM mode we can achieve atomic resolution and identify isolated Ag ions and Ag clusters as small as 6 atoms.

Figures

Figure 1. Ag₆ clusters in zeolite A (LTA), red atoms correspond to O and blue atoms correspond to Si and Al, coordinated by up to 8 silver atoms. A linear Ag₃ unit is also shown in the cage on the top right. b) 6-ring, marked in a) with a black arrow.

Figure 2. a) Model for the LTA framework, *Fm-3c*. b) Inverse FFT image recorded along the [001] direction. The FFT diffractogram, shown inset, was indexed assuming the *Fm-3c* symmetry. c) Simulated HAADF-STEM image of the crystal framework along the [001] direction using multislice calculations. Parameters used: 300 kV, $C_s = 0$ mm, defocus value = 0, probe convergence angle = 24.5 mrad, collection angle = 50–200 mrad. A representation of the zeolite A unit cell is superimposed in parts b) & c).

Figure 3. Aberration corrected STEM-HAADF micrographs of dehydrated AgA recorded along a) [001], b) [011] and c) [111] directions.

Figure 4. a) Aberration-corrected STEM-HAADF image of AgA along the [001] direction, where the white spots are single atomic columns and the black arrows point to Ag clusters in the alpha cages. b) and c) Fourier filtered images of the atomic distribution where the 4 columns of Ag at the corners of the sodalite cage are separated by 4.72 Å and each sodalite cage is separated by 7.41 Å; the Ag₆ cluster is also observed in these cages. d) Proposed model with the Ag atoms in grey. e) Intensity profiles performed on the atoms marked as 1, 2 and 3 in c) and 4, 5 and 6 with the interatomic distance between these atoms being 2.70 Å. f) Multislice STEM simulation along the [001] direction using: 300 kV, C_s = 0 mm, defocus value = 0, probe convergence semiangle = 24 mrad, collection angle = 70–200 mrad. The experimental image is presented alongside and in both cases the zeolite framework signal is marked by a white circle.

Supporting information

S1

Table 1: Refined atomic parameters obtained from Rietveld analysis of dehydrated silver zeolite A^a

Atom	Wyckoff position	X	Y	Z	Occupancy	B
Si(1)	96i	0	0.0939(3)	0.1841(3)	1	0.70(4)
Al(1)	96i	0	0.1853(3)	0.0914(3)	1	0.70(4)
O(1)	96i	0	0.1109(2)	0.2479(7)	1	1.38(9)
O(2)	96i	0	0.1476(6)	0.1515(6)	1	1.38(9)
O(3)	192j	0.0526(3)	0.0568(3)	0.1714(2)	1	1.38(9)
Ag(1)	64g	0.0964(3)	0.0964(3)	0.0964(3)	0.9706	2.90(4)
Ag(2)	96i	0	0.2227(2)	0.2089(3)	0.1942	2.90(4)
Ag(3)	48e	0	0	0.0806(3)	0.1692	2.90(4)

^a Lattice Parameter: $a = 24.66358(7)$ Å, space group: $Fm\bar{3}c$, $\chi^2 = 1.14$, $R_{wp} = 8.89$, $R_p = 6.99$.

Note: An Ag position was also refined at (0.25, 0.07(8), 0.07(8)) but was removed as it had a very low occupancy and did not improve the fit significantly.

Powder synchrotron XRD Rietveld fit of dehydrated silver zeolite A (refinement done using the computer program TOPAS¹).

1. A. Coelho, Topas Academic Version 4.1. Computer Software, Topas Academic, Coelho Software, Brisbane, 2007.

S2

S2 Effect of beam damage on zeolite crystallites of AgA . a) AgA particle where the red rectangle marks the amorphous area caused by the electron beam. Ag nanoparticles of several nm are observed due to the reduction of Ag^+ in presence of water and oxygen. b) A hole in the structure as observed when the beam was stopped at that position for a few seconds. c) intensity signal profile(arbitrary units) plotted over the white arrow marked in b.

In this image two effects produced as a consequence of the radiolytic damage which occur in zeolites can be observed. In the figure S2a degradation through *inelastic* scattering which results in loss of crystallinity can be observed in the area marked by a rectangle. In figure b a process of mass loss by the appearance of a hole of 3 nm in diameter is displayed. The hole was surrounded by an amorphous area and that amount of silica might be evaporated within the column.

S3

Figure S3 atomic resolution aberration corrected STEM-HAADF images of AgA recorded along of a) the [110] orientation and b) the [111] orientation, where the white spots correspond to silver atomic columns.

S4

Figure S4 Effect of the probe size on the STEM-HAADF simulated images in focus. a) 0.7 Å; b) 1.7 Å and c) 2.5 Å.

S5

Figure S5 Raw data corresponding to figures 4b and 4c.